

TANGENT

REPORT ON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES (INCLUDING COOPERATION WITH OTHER PROJECTS). SECOND RELEASE.

D8.7

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https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCjhz4kwEm_sTHj7fE4zXToA

For further information please visit <http://www.tangent-h2020.eu/>

Executive summary

D8.7 report on dissemination activities presents cooperation with other sister projects and reviews the progress achieved from month 19 (March 2023) to month 39 (November 2024) of the TANGENT project. Chapter 1 introduces the objectives and intended audience of the project. Chapter 2 and Chapter 3 present the updated and newly created physical and digital project identity, which includes the sister projects and project marketing and promotional materials, such as video, newsletters, website and social media channels. Then, the report breakdowns the publications (Chapter 4), events and conferences (Chapter 5), which showcased the project's outcomes, results and findings. Chapter 6 is devoted to collaborations with external partners. It describes the activities of the 4FRONT Cluster and Multimodal Traffic Management (MTM) Cluster ((sister projects) as well as the TANGENT Advisory Board and Forum. Finally, the report gives a brief overview of the upcoming dissemination activities planned for the post-project period.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Full Name
AB	Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
TRA	Transport Research Arena
TRB	Transportation Research Board
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse.
AB	Advisory Board
WS	Workshop

1 Introduction

The strategy, procedures, and organisation for successful dissemination have remained consistent throughout the project. The dissemination activities have been performed under the Dissemination and Communication Plan (Deliverable 8.1) which was created by the first project months and submitted in December 2021. The plan has outlined dissemination activities, project branding, identification of materials, and communication strategies for the project's duration. Dissemination activities have been continued throughout the project, with contributions from all consortium partners. The consortium has garnered interest from numerous stakeholders and interested parties.

The focus of TANGENT's dissemination efforts has transitioned from raising awareness at the beginning of the project action to supporting exploitation activities. Stakeholders can now test and validate project results, and potential customers can explore their application. This aligns with the long-term goal of sustaining project outcomes.

The present document covers the dissemination activities carried out from March 2023 to November 2024 (M19 to M39 of the project). The report also includes a plan for disseminating project activities after its completion.

2 Physical Project Identity Updates

TANGENT’s digital and physical identity are presented in the D8.1, D8.2 and D8.3. This section presents only major updates.

2.1 Sister project leaflets and roll-up banner

A leaflet for the 4Front Consortium was designed and delivered by POLIS early 2023. It was later updated to the Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster in 2024, to present the cluster of sister projects and showcase the common goals. A roll-up banner was also created and printed with the cooperation of the new sister projects of the MTMC.

Figure 1: MTMC Leaflet (left & centre) and MTMC roll-up banner (right)

3 Digital Project Identity Updates

3.1 TANGENT Video: “The TANGENT Tool: an explainer video”

In cooperation with the Peaberry Up (a design company), POLIS produced a video explaining the TANGENT dashboard. The animated video presents how the TANGENT dashboard and tools support multimodal traffic management in real cases. Link video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lrwu79llx4k>

Figure 2: Snapshots from the video storyboard

3.2 Website and Social Media

TANGENT’s **website** has been regularly updated, with over 29 original articles on events, news items explaining key deliverables, project milestones, involvement in conferences, etc. The website receives approximately 200 unique users each month on average. The domain name is www.tangent-h2020.eu.

To give an overview of the website’s activities, we have extracted data from the last year (**October 2023 to October 2024**). The three graphs below show respectively the number of active users, the pages they viewed the most and where they were based. The information has been retrieved on 21 Oct.2024.

Figure 3: TANGENT website data: the number of active users, the pages they viewed the most and where they were based

TANGENT's [X account \(former Twitter\)](#) followers grew from 69 followers in February 2023 to 134 by October 2024 and on [LinkedIn](#) from 179 in February 2023 to 517 in October 2024.

3.3 Newsletters

TANGENT published six **newsletters** covering project activities, events, deliverables, outcomes, and progress on use cases. These newsletters were co-authored by POLIS, ID4MOBILITY, NTUA, and DEUSTO.

The TANGENT newsletter currently has 60 subscribers.

The newsletters are available on the [website](#).

Figure 4: TANGENT's fourth, fifth and last newsletters

4 Publications since March 2023

4.1 Press releases

During the second period TANGENT has issued or will soon issue (post-project results) the following press releases listed below. An additional press release was issued in the previous reporting period, meeting the KPI of 8 press releases throughout the duration of the project. These prominently feature the project's key results and outcomes, with a particular focus on the four pilot initiatives. These 8 press releases serve as valuable communication tools to inform stakeholders, the public, and media outlets about the project's final achievements and significance.

Date	Name of outlet	Title	Partner	Outreach Level
11.2023	Magazine of faculty of Engineering	TANGENT: mejora de las operaciones de tráfico optimizando la gestión de la oferta y la demanda de transporte	DEUSTO	National
01.2024	Agenda Digitale	Gestire meglio il traffico grazie allo scambio dati: il progetto TANGENT	CEFRIEL	National
04.2024	Cefriel website	TANGENT: migliorare la gestione del traffico stradale grazie allo scambio dati	CEFRIEL	National
11.2024	POLIS Website	Planned (TBA)	POLIS	Global

Table 1: Press releases issued on national and international levels from March 2023 to November 2024

4.2 Scientific Publications and Conference Papers

TANGENT published 22 articles and scientific papers in specialised media, magazines, journals, and through conferences to inform target transport professionals and urban mobility practitioners (see Table 2). The FAIR principles ('findability', 'accessibility', 'interoperability' and 'reusability') of open research through open peer-reviewed publications were employed. The consortium registered their research publications on the EU Open Research Repository (<https://zenodo.org/>).

Date	Title of Periodical / Series / Outlet	Title of Item / Article	Author(s)
05/2023	15th ITS European Congress, Lisbon, Portugal	TANGENT – Beyond Transportation Dashboarding	Tiago Dias, Hannah Tune, Antonio Masegosa, Athina Tympakianaki, Ynte Vanderhoydonc, Leire Serrano, Ana Vieira da Silva, Lara Trigueiro Moura

Date	Title of Periodical / Series / Outlet	Title of Item / Article	Author(s)
05/2023	4th International workshop on Knowledge Graph Construction	Composable Semantic Data Transformation Pipelines with Chimera	Marco Grassi, Mario Scrocca, Marco Comerio, Alessio Carenini, Irene Celino
06/2023	ISTDM 2023, Ispra, Italy	Online Demand Forecasting with Spatial-Temporal Graph Attention Networks: A Proof of Concept	Monica Dominguez, Athina Tympakianaki, Ferran Torrent, Tessa Hayman, Josep Perarnau, Jordi Casas
09/2023	2023 IEEE 26th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)	A Taxonomy of Signal Vehicle Coupled Control from a Mathematical Programming Perspective	Arka Ghosh; Juan S. Angarita-Zapata; Antonio D. Masegosa; Ander Arriandiaga Laresgoiti
04/2024	TRA 2024, Dublin	Software patterns and architectural decisions for a Next-Generation Traffic Management System in the TANGENT project	Tiago Dias, Ana V. Silva, Lara Trigueiro Moura
04/2024	TRA 2024, Dublin	The TANGENT project architecture: towards new traffic management approaches	Hugo Landaluce, Antonio Masegosa, Leire Serrano, Arka Gosh, Ander Arrandiaga, Tiago Dias, Ana V. Silva, Lara Trigueiro Moura
04/2024	TRA 2024, Dublin	Mobility data harmonisation: the TANGENT solution.	Comerio M., Fiano A., Grassi M., Scrocca M.
04/2024	TRA 2024, Dublin	The TANGENT governance model for mobility data sharing	Azzini A., Comerio M., Metta S., Scrocca M.
04/2024	TRA 2024, Dublin	Predicting Demand and Supply in a Real-Time Traffic Management Framework	Athina Tympakianaki, Monica Dominguez, Jordi Casas, Mohammadmahdi Rahimiasl, Ynte Vanderhoydonc

Date	Title of Periodical / Series / Outlet	Title of Item / Article	Author(s)
05/2024	Navigating Data in the Field of Traffic Management	Navigating Data in the Field of Traffic Management	Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster (MTMC)
06/2024	IEEE Access	Survey on best practices in data-driven approaches for traffic state predictions (submitted)	Ynte Vanderhoydonc, Mohammadmahdi Rahimiasl, Panagiotis Fafoutellis, Eleni I. Vlahogianni, Eleni Mantouka, Arka Ghosh, Juan S. Angarita-Zapata, Athina Tympakianaki, Antonio D. Masegosa, and Siegfried Mercelis
08/2024	IEEE Access	Emerging Trends in Machine Learning assisted Optimization Techniques Across Intelligent Transportation systems	Blessing Ito Afolayan, Arka Ghosh, Jenny Fajardo Calderin, and Antonio D. Mesagosa Arredondo
09/2024	ITS World 2024	The TANGENT Dashboard as a Next Generation Traffic and Transport Management System	Tiago Dias, Ana Vieira da Silva, Daniel Matos
09/2024	ITS World 2024	Smart Transport Infrastructures Classification	Tiago Dias, Ana Vieira da Silva, Lara Trigueiro Moura, Daniel Matos
09/2024	Journal of Urban Mobility or European Transport Research Review	Real-time prediction and denoising: deep learning approaches for noisy traffic data (Peer review after ETC 2024 for submission)	Mohammadmahdi Rahimiasl, Ynte Vanderhoydonc, Siegfried Mercelis
10/2024	CoDIT 2024	Enhancing public transport systems through scalable real-time forecasting solutions for the case study of Rennes	Mohammadmahdi Rahimiasl, Ynte Vanderhoydonc, Siegfried Mercelis
10/2024	Multimodal Traffic Management: Roadmap for 2030 and Beyond	Multimodal Traffic Management: Roadmap for 2030 and Beyond	Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster (MTMC)

Date	Title of Periodical / Series / Outlet	Title of Item / Article	Author(s)
10/2024	ASCE	"Optimization of Dynamic Congestion Pricing Strategy and its Effects on Traffic Flow – A Case Study of Greater Manchester City"	Arka Gosh, Samra Sarwar, Antonio D. Masegosa, Ander Arriandiaga Laresgoiti
11/2024	ISWC 2024 , Baltimore, USA	Intelligent Urban Traffic Management via Semantic Interoperability across Multiple Heterogeneous Mobility Data Sources	Mario Scrocca, Marco Grassi, Marco Comerio, Valentina Anita Carriero, Tiago Delgado Dias, Ana Vieira Da Silva, Irene Celino
11/2024	3PGCIC-2024 , Italy	Transfer learning for traffic state predictions in small and medium-sized cities	Mohammadmahdi Rahimiasl, Ynte Vanderhoydonc, Siegfried Mercelis, Laure De Cock, Thomas Kusmirczak, and Tamara De Swert
04/2025	11th International Conference on Vehicle Technology and Intelligent Transport Systems	TANGENT back-end service for real-time traffic forecasting (submitted)	Mohammadmahdi Rahimiasl, Andreas Durt, Ynte Vanderhoydonc, Siegfried Mercelis
06/2025	American Society of Civil Engineering (ASCE) for the International Conference on Transportation and Development	Optimization of Dynamic Congestion Pricing Strategy – A Case Study of Greater Manchester City (accepted)	Arka Gosha, Samra Sarwara, Antonio D. Masegosa, Ander Arriandiaga Laresgoitia

Table 2: List of Scientific Publications and Conference Papers from March 2023 to November 2024 (including submitted and in press)

5 Events and Conferences since March 2023

TANGENT *actively participated* in various events and conferences during the project's second phase (M19 - M39) to enhance visibility and disseminate and exploit key results, findings and outcomes. A comprehensive list of these are presented below in Table 3.

For events from September 2021 to February 2023, please see D8.3.

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
SIS on Technology for leveraging the traffic management of the future - 4FRONT Cluster	15th ITS European Congress	22/5/2023	Lisbon	European	A-to-Be TfGM	A-to-Be (Tiago Dias) and Hannah Tunne (TfGM) presented: TANGENT - Enhanced Data Processing Techniques for Dynamic Management of Multimodal Traffic
15th ITS European Congress	ERTICO	22/5/2023	Lisbon	European	TfGM, A-to-Be, CEFRIEL, Carris	presentation
ISTDM2023 (International Symposium on Transportation Data & Modelling)	European Commission	19-22/06/2023	Ispra	European	Aimsun	Presentation on TANGENT solutions for demand prediction (WP4)
hEART 2023	European Association for Research in Transportation & ITPS, Zurich	6-8/09/2023	Zurich	European	Aimsun	Aimsun will organise a workshop to present the work performed in different EU-funded research projects, including TANGENT (focusing on WP4 demand and

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
						supply tasks) - Open to other suggestions and involvement of partners who plan to attend the conference
ICTR 2023	CERTH and HITE, Athens	20-22/09/2023	Heraklion, Greece	European	NTUA	Oral presentation
IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)	IEEE and Tecnalia Research & Innovation	23/09/2023	Bilbao, Spain	International	DEUSTO, NTUA	Special Session + Paper DEUSTO Abstract: "A Taxonomy of Signal Vehicle Coupled Control from a Mathematical Programming Perspective"
IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)	IEEE and Tecnalia Research & Innovation	24/09/2023	Bilbao	International	Aimsun, imec	Aimsun organised a tutorial session on incident detection. The TANGENT project will be represented by Aimsun and imec (Mahdi) https://2023.ieee-itsc.org/accepted-tutorials/
IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)	IEEE and Tecnalia Research & Innovation	25/09/2023	Bilbao	International	Deusto	Deusto presented an accepted paper to one of the special sessions in the conference

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
<u>Systems (ITSC)</u>						
<u>IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)</u>	IEEE and Tecnalia Research & Innovation	24-28/09/2023	Bilbao	International	NTUA	Oral presentations
<u>Urban Mobility Days</u>	European Commission	4-6/10/2023	Seville	European	DEUSTO	stand w/4FRONT projects
<u>Urban Mobility Days</u>	European Commission	4-6/10/2023	Seville	European	POLIS	stand w/4FRONT projects
<u>Portugal Smart Cities Summit 2023</u>	City of Lisbon Municipality	10/10/2023	Lisbon	National	CARRIS	<p>Dissemination of WP2 TANGENT activity on metadata</p> <p>CARRIS will make a presentation at the event, in which we will relate the challenges PTOs face when dealing with large-scale events and disruptions. We shall present the TANGENT's proposed approach to deal with these events and highlight the potential of these tools to help plan and manage operations during such events.</p>

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
Modelling World 2023	Landor LINKS, UK	2/11/2023	Birmingham	International	Aimsun	Presentation of work performed within WP4 on demand estimation
NAPCORE Mobility Data Days	NAPCORE	7-9/11/2023	Budapest	European	Cefriel	Presentation of work performed within WP4 on demand estimation
Nordic Aimsun Meeting	Aimsun	27-29/11/2023	Online	European	Aimsun	Dissemination of WP4 TANGENT developments on the real-time traffic management framework and demonstration of its application focusing on the demand estimation problem
POLIS Conference	POLIS	29-30/11/2023	Leuven	European	POLIS, ID4CAR	stand
Digital Twin for Cities	KTH, Royal Institute of Technology	18/12/2023	Stockholm	European	AIMSUN	Presentation: Presented the TANGENT project, referred to key solutions and real-time monitoring and forecasting framework
Transport AI conference	Landor LINKS, UK	23/01/2024	UK	European	Aimsun	Dissemination and presentation of WP4 TANGENT on traffic predictions (benchmarking with Aimsun's solutions) on the

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
						Manchester network
TRB 2024	Yes	24/01/2024	USA	International	Aimsun	Dissemination of TANGENT at Aimsun's booth, distributions of brochures
Road Research Transport Conference (RTR Conference)	European Commission, ERTRAC, 2ZERO, CCAM	05-07/02/2024	Brussels	European	POLIS, RUPPRECHT	Presentation / Panel discussion with 4 Front
4FRONT CLUSTER MEETING Network & Traffic Management Systems (NTM)	MTMC (Cluster)	08-09/02/2024	Brussels	European	POLIS, DEUSTO, AIMSUN, RUPPRECHT	Presentation / Workshops
Connecting Europe Days	Co-organised by the European Commission and the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU	2-5/04/2024	Brussels	European	MTMC	Exhibition with Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster
TRA conference 2024	Co-organised by the European Commission	15-18/04/2024	Dublin	International	DEUSTO, Cefriel, A-to-Be	DEUSTO/A-To-B: The TANGENT project architecture: towards new traffic management approaches

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
						<p>Cefriel: Mobility data harmonisation: the TANGENT solution</p> <p>Cefriel: TANGENT governance model for mobility data sharing</p> <p>NTUA: Travel choice behaviour modelling; Congestion duration modelling; Stakeholder preferences analysis.</p> <p>A-to-Be: Software patterns and architectural aspects for implementation for a Next-Generation Traffic Management System in the TANGENT project</p> <p>PANEL PARTICIPATION : ORCHESTRA & FRONTIER Final Conference - Multimodal and resilient traffic management of the future, A-to-Be; SS3.7: Advancing Resilience of Transport Operations and Infrastructure - A-to-Be</p>

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
TRA conference 2024	Co-organised by the European Commission	15-18/04/2024	Dublin	International	Aimsun, NTUA	AIMSUN/imec/NTU Demand and Supply Predictions in a Real-Time Traffic Management Framework
TRA conference 2024	Co-organised by the European Commission	15-18/04/2024	Dublin	International	NTUA	Poster presentation
PDI, Connectivity and Cooperation for CCAM Solutions	IN-MOVE by Railgrup	5/30/2024	online	International	A-to-Be	Presentation: TANGENT: Dynamic Management of Multimodal Traffic in Athens, Lisbon, Manchester and Rennes
25th IEEE International Conference on Mobile Data Management, MAURO: 1st International Workshop on Impact of Algorithms and Services on the Urban Ecosystem	Organizing committee with support of the following EU Horizon projects and organizations: Green.Dat. , AI , SoBigData++ , URBAI	24-27/6/2024	Brussels, Belgium	International	imec	Presentation: 4 slides with reference in presentation "Transfer learning for traffic state predictions in small and medium-sized cities." "The CitCom.ai TEF as incubator"
1st International Workshop on Distributed Intelligence for Sustainable Solutions in conjunction	University of Antwerp	13-15/11/2024	San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy	International	imec	Paper: "Transfer learning for traffic state predictions in small and medium-sized cities"

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
with the 19th 3PGCIC Conference on P2P, Parallel, Grid, Cloud and Internet Computing						
Forum Mobilités Transitions	ID4MOBILITY	07/2024	Rennes, France	National	ID4MOBILITY, Rennes Métropole, Keolis, AIMSUN france	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stand to promote Rennes case study with a demo of the tool - Participation to a round table with other EU projects
CoDIT 2024	International Program Committee, sponsored by three major IEEE societies together with the International Federation of Automatic Control	1-4/07/2024	Valletta, Malta	International	imec	Short paper "Enhancing public transport systems through scalable real-time forecasting solutions for the case study of Rennes"
IFAC CTS 2024	IFAC	01-03-07/2024	Ayia Napa, Cyprus	International	NTUA	Oral presentation
Urban Transport Group	TfGM/UTG	07/2024	Manchester	National	TfGM	Presentation / Workshops
European Transport Conference 2024 (ETC 24)	Association for European Transport	18-20/09/2024	Antwerp	European	imec	"Data preprocessing for real-time traffic forecasting of noisy journey times – A case study of Greater

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
						Manchester” – Paper.
ITS World 2024	Participating w/ communication	16-20/09/2024	Dubai	Worldwide	A-to-Be	The TANGENT Dashboard as a Next Generation Traffic and Transport Management System (oral communication)
ITS World 2024	Participating w/ communication	16-20/09/2024	Dubai	Worldwide	A-to-Be	Smart Transport Infrastructures Classification (oral communication)
ITS World 2024	MTM Cluster	16-20/09/2024	Dubai	Worldwide	A-to-Be	Special Interest Session panel: "Advanced Multimodal Network and Traffic Management: the latest advances of EU research"
CIVITAS Forum 2024	CIVITAS	1-3/10/2024	Parma, Italy	European	DEUSTO, RUPPRECHT, POLIS	Session: T2.2 session - Enhancing Traffic Management with Digital Twins and AI & Exhibitor
11th ECTRI TG TMM Webinar	ECTRI	10/10/2024	Online	European	Deusto	Presentation: Computer-optimized Design for Transport Network Management
23rd International Semantic Web Conference	SWSA	11/11/2024	Baltimore	worldwide	Cefriel	Paper: Intelligent Urban Traffic Management via Semantic

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
						Interoperability across Multiple Heterogeneous Mobility Data Sources in small and medium-sized cities.
Congreso ITS Euskadi	MLC ITS Euskadi	15/11/2024	Bilbao, Spain	Regional	Deusto	Presentation: "Proyecto europeo TANGENT: herramientas de gestión de tráfico multiagente"
2024 POLIS Conference	POLIS	27-28/11/2024	Karlsruhe, Germany	European	Rupprecht, Deusto	Session "TANGENT: Lessons from coordinated and dynamic multimodal traffic management implementation"
2024 POLIS Conference	POLIS	27-28/11/2024	Karlsruhe, Germany	European	POLIS	Exhibition at POLIS stand
11th International Conference on Vehicle Technology and Intelligent Transport Systems (VEHITS 2025)	INSTICC	2-4/4/2025	Porto, Portugal	International	imec	Submitted abstract "TANGENT back-end service for real-time traffic forecasting"

Table 3: Database of TANGENT participation in conferences and events from March 2023 to November 2024

TANGENT also *organised* several events, which are listed in Table 4:

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
AB Session 1: Advancing Mode Choice Predictions: Exploring State-of-the-Art Methods and Emerging Data Sources	Rupprecht	22.06.2023	Online	Internal	Various partners	Presentation / Workshop
AB Session 2: Advancing Mobility Strategies: State-of-the-Art Traffic Forecasting and Generation of Transport Policy and Response Plans Using Automatic Design Concept	Rupprecht	23.06.2023	Online	Internal	Various partners	Presentation / Workshop
AB Session 3: Unlocking Data Collaboration and Assessing Smart Infrastructure Indexes	Rupprecht	26.06.2023	Online	Internal	Various partners	Presentation / Workshop
Webinar #1: 'Navigating through Network and Traffic Management: An Urban Phenomenon'	Rupprecht	15/11/2023	Online	Global	Various Partners	Webinar
AB Sessions 4-6	Rupprecht	01.12.2023	Online	Internal	AIMSUN, IMEC, DEUSTO, NTUA, ID4M	Presentation / Workshop

Title of Event	Organiser	Date	Location	DISS. Level	Partner Attending	TANGENT Promotion
Webinar #2: 'Real-Time Traffic Modelling and Forecasting Tools'	Rupprecht	31/01/2024	Online	Global	Ynte Vanderhoydonc, imec Athina Tympakianaki, Aimsun	Webinar
The TANGENT Tool: an explainer video	POLIS	20/02/2024	Online	Global	N/A	Project Video
Webinar #3: Transport Network Optimisation and Arbitration Models	Rupprecht	21/05/2024	Online	Global	Arka Ghosh, Universidad de Deusto / Marios Giouroukelis, National Technical University of Athens	Webinar
Final Event	POLIS / DEUSTO	16/10/2024	In-Person & Online	Global	All	Event
Webinar #4: titled Integrated Tool for Cooperative Traffic Management and Results of Case Study Implementation	Rupprecht	30/10/2024	Online	Global	Tiago Dias, A-to-Be / Lucie Tristant, ID4Mobility	Webinar

Table 4: Database of events and webinars organised by TANGENT from March 2023 to November 2024

6 Clustering activities with other EU projects

During the project lifetime, TANGENT has been a part of the **4Front Cluster**. It embraced four sister projects funded under the same call topic, “MG-2-11-2020 - Network and traffic management for future mobility”: DIT4TRAM, FRONTIER, TANGENT and ORCHESTRA. From April 2024 onwards, it was enlarged and renamed **Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster (MTMC)**. Three Horizon Europe projects were added under the call topic “HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02-05 - Advanced multimodal network and traffic management for seamless door-to-door mobility of passengers and freight transport”, namely SYNCHROMODE, ACUMEN and DELPHI.

The MTMC cluster continued in the footsteps of the 4Front Cluster, having regular online meetings to discuss cooperation opportunities, two common papers, and more. The projects have collaborated in various events, further details follow:

6.1 Publications & Others

Horizon Results Booster - MODULE B, Portfolio Dissemination Plan (design and execution)

From October 2023 to October 2024, the 4Front Cluster (4 projects) and then the Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster (7 projects) participated in the Horizon Results Booster Module B. Outputs produced include:

- Each project submitted a thorough pre-assessment survey through the Horizon Results Booster platform
- The 4Front cluster dissemination plan
- MTMC logo and visual identity

Figure 5: MTMC logo

- MTMC video: <https://youtu.be/NEG5lzFVF20?feature=shared>
- Design of the MTMC Roadmap

Publication 1: Navigating Data in the Field of Traffic Management

In May 2024, the Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster, in cooperation with the MobiDataLab project, published a policy brief on enhancing multimodal traffic management through improved data sharing and governance.

The collection of the brief’s content started in June 2023 during an online workshop. Technical partners handling, collecting and/or working on data came together to identify challenges, opportunities and recommendations linked to data ecosystems, governance, regulations, standards and exchange. The brief was written by the 4Front Cluster (FRONTIER, ORCHESTRA, DIT4TRAM and TANGENT).

Furthermore, it was reviewed and validated by the new cluster projects: SYNCHROMODE, DELPHI and ACUMEN.

Access the Cluster Data Sharing Policy Brief: <https://tangent-h2020.eu/a-policy-brief-on-data-sharing-for-traffic-management/>

Multimodal Traffic Management: Roadmap for 2030 and beyond

The roadmap is a collaborative effort of the MTMC Cluster, starting in late 2023 and spearheaded through a two-day in-person workshop in February in Brussels (see section events below).

This roadmap sets forth a comprehensive strategic vision to transform Europe’s transport networks into multimodal, sustainable, and resilient systems, aligning with EU climate neutrality and resilience goals and preparing the transport sector for future challenges and opportunities. The roadmap focuses on three main interrelated areas: a) Technologies and Services, b) Data, and c) Policies, each of which is critical for achieving a seamless, efficient, and resilient multimodal transport system by 2030 and beyond. [Link to the roadmap.](#)

Figure 6: Cover of the Multimodal Traffic Management Roadmap

6.2 Events

Urban Mobility Days, Seville, 4 to 6 Oct 2023

At the Urban Mobility Days in Seville, TANGENT was invited to have a joint exhibitor stand in the main hall with its sister projects. During an exhibition tour, Leire Serrano presented TANGENT to Paloma Aba Garrote (Director in CINEA) and Rosaline van der Vlies (Clean Planet Director in the European Commission). Arkha Gosh also presented TANGENT in a pitch presentation in the plenary.

Figure 7: TANGENT at the Urban Mobility Days in Seville, 4 - 6 Oct 2023

Road Transport Research Conference 2024 in Brussels - 5 to 7 February 2024

Juliette Thijs from the POLIS Network presented the main results and impacts of TANGENT in the "Network and Traffic Management for Future Mobility" session. The panel included the three other 4Front traffic management projects: Sascha Hoogendoorn-Lanser (DIT4TraM Project), Panos Georgakis (FRONTIER EU Project) and Runar Søråsen (Orchestra2020).

Figure 8: TANGENT at the Road Transport Research Conference 2024 in Brussels, 5-7 February 2024

Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster and 2 CCAM projects 2-day in-person meeting at POLIS Office - 8 and 9 February 2024

During two days, TANGENT and 8 other projects on network and traffic management and CCAM took part in intensive workshops to define a vision for the future of mobility. Deusto and POLIS participated in the session. The goal was to start working on the preparation of the revised Strategic Research and Implementation Roadmap for NTM, including:

- the NTM baseline and state of the art including data sharing, sensors & devices, collaborative decision making, governance and arbitration, as well as monitoring, estimations and predictions.
- how to achieve policy objectives and targets linked to physical/digital infrastructure, the integration of transport modes into a multimodal network for passengers and freight, the integration of CCAM, reducing external costs and the cost of mobility for all, and enhanced local and/or regional capacity for governance and innovation.
- the definition of the first steps for a Strategic Implementation Plan including roadmaps linked to technology, operations and organisations, and policy.

Figure 9: TANGENT at MTMC and 2 CCAM projects - 2-day in-person meeting at POLIS Office, 8 - 9 February 2024

Connecting Europe Days, Brussels - 2 to 5 February 2024

The Connecting Europe Days was the opportunity to officially launch the Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster. The seven projects were represented at a common stand at the conference, and the video produced by the Horizon Booster was showcased.

Figure 10: TANGENT at the Connecting Europe Days, Brussels, 2 - 5 February 2024

Transport Research Arena, 15 to 18 April in Dublin (Ireland) & FRONTIER-ORCHESTRA Final Conference at TRA 2024

TANGENT had extensive coverage at TRA (3 technical papers, 2 posters, special sessions, etc.). In regards to the MTMC, TANGENT participated in the shared stand (roll-up and leaflets, with the presence of project consortium members). In addition, David Watts (TfGM) was on a panel discussion at the ORCHESTRA-FRONTIER final conference.

Figure 11: TANGENT at the Transport Research Arena, Dublin (Ireland), 15 - 18 April 2024

ITS World Congress, Dubai - 16 to 20 September 2024

TANGENT participated in the “Advanced multimodal network and traffic management: the latest advances of EU research session with projects from the Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster: DELPHI, SYNCHROMODE, ACUMEN, ORCHESTRA, and FRONTIER.

Figure 12: TANGENT at the ITS World Congress, Dubai, 16 - 20 September 2024

CIVITAS Forum, Parma - 1 to 3 October 2024

At the CIVITAS Forum, TANGENT was selected as an exhibitor alongside other EU-funded projects. The project participated in session 16 “Enhancing Traffic Management with Digital Twins and AI” alongside 7 other projects and moderated by Thiago Tavares. On this session the release of the “Multimodal Traffic Management: Roadmap for 2030 and beyond” were announced.

Figure 13: TANGENT at the CIVITAS Forum, Parma (Italy), 1 - 3 October 2024

TANGENT Final Event, Brussels – 16 October 2024

The TANGENT final event was organized in Brussels on 16 October 2024. The project officer Thiago Tavares welcomed the project partners, invited guests and Advisory Board members. The event took place in a hybrid format, both in-person and virtual. The event activities were translated during the live stream, the record of which will be available on the project website. During this activity the TANGENT dashboard and related solutions, research methodologies and tested technologies for traffic management; the technical challenges in multimodal network and traffic management; the view of transport managers on the TANGENT tools tested in the cities: Rennes, Greater Manchester and Lisbon and the policies and governance structures behind multi-actor cooperation in traffic management were

TANGENT project (GA no 955273): TANGENT final event		TANGENT project (GA no 955273): TANGENT final event	
Subject: TANGENT final event Date: 16 of October 2024 Event venue: Les Ateliers des Tanneurs, Rue des Tanneurs 60A, 1000 Brussels https://maps.app.goo.gl/6A4wGBd8r3tbaG7 You can join online with Zoom: - Follow this link: https://shorturl.at/m56xx		16th of October 2024	
16th of October 2024		16th of October 2024	
9:15-9:35	Welcome words& Overview of TANGENT	Leire Serrano - DEUSTO	
9:35-9:45	Challenges in traffic management	Thiago Tavares – CINEA (European Commission)	
9:45-10:35	TANGENT solution integrated (Presentation and demo) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service 1- Enhanced Information Service for Multimodal Transport Management (Dashboard) Service 2 - Real-Time Traffic Management Services Service 3 -Transport Network Optimization for Transport Authorities 	Tiago Dias - A-to-Be	
10:35-11:00		COFFEE BREAK	
11:00-12:15	TANGENT research technologies for traffic management – key findings (Presentation) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Travel behaviour analysis (NTUA) Transport prediction and simulation (imec, Aimsun) Transport network optimization (Deusto) Data gathering, harmonisation& fusion (Cefriel) 	Eleni Vlahogianni - NTUA Athina Tympakianaki-Aimsun Ynte Vanderhoydonc-imec Antonio Masegosa-Deusto Marco Comerio-CEFRIEL	
12:15-12:45	Technical challenges in multimodal network& traffic management – (Round table)	Eleni Vlahogianni - NTUA Athina Tympakianaki-Aimsun Ynte Vanderhoydonc-imec Antonio Masegosa-Deusto Marco Comerio-Cefriel Tiago Dias - A-to-Be	
12:45-13:30		LUNCH BREAK	
13:30-14:00	Presentation of TANGENT testing results (Presentation)	Lucie Tristant - ID4MOBILITY Geert Koops – Pantelis	
14:00-14:30	The view of transport managers: Testing of TANGENT in the case studies: Rennes, Greater Manchester and Lisbon (Round table)	Hannah Tune-Transport for Greater Manchester	
		14:30-15:00 Multi-actor cooperation in traffic management: governance& policy (Presentation) Daniel Franco-Rupprecht Geert Koops - Pantelis	
		15:00-15:20 COFFEE BREAK	
		15:20-16:00 Future of TANGENT tools: exploitation, policy and future roadmap (Workshop) Moderator Daniel Franco- Rupprecht	
		End of event	

Figure 14: TANGENT Final Event, Brussels, 16 October 2024

presented, demonstrated and discussed. The agenda of the event and photo from the event are presented in Figure 14 and Figure 15:

Figure 15: TANGENT Final Event, Brussels, 16 October 2024

MTMC Webinar – 12 November 2024

The MTMC is organising a webinar on 12 November on “Network and Traffic Management: current status and future developments in EU R&D activities”. CINEA Project Officer Thiago Tavares will be an invited speaker to introduce second-Generation R&D Projects. Moreover, EU Project Outcomes for Urban Traffic Management (FRONTIER and TANGENT) will be showcased.

7 TANGENT Advisory Board and Forum

Since February 2023 the **TANGENT Advisory Board and Forum** supports the consortium to overlook the project from an external, independent perspective providing strategic input, guidance and support to the project on an annual basis. The task was orchestrated under WP1 activity T1.4 and led by Rupprecht Consult. The Advisory Board (AB) consists of twelve stakeholders representing researchers, local authorities, industry, and transport operators. As a strategic body, the AB met eight times during the project (see Table 6).

Figure 16: Left: AB online Meeting record screen and Right: Mentimeter results from polls during Webinar 2 (extracted from D1.5)

The TANGENT Forum is a wider, exclusive group of professionals who can closely follow project activities, events, and results. The project outcomes and products have been validated and promoted by the Forum members. The TANGENT Forum space remains unchanged from its initial configuration:

- A TANGENT Cities page sharing information regarding four pilot cities’ goals and vision in the implementation of TANGENT tools and services (Athens, Greater Manchester, Lisbon and Rennes)
- A Discussion Forum for a dialog on traffic management and other mobility challenges.
- TANGENT webinars

TANGENT regularly organized webinars to present key results, tools, and gather stakeholder feedback. 159 participants attended these online events. Recordings are available on [the project's YouTube channel](#), along with additional materials used during the sessions. Rupprecht Consult moderated these webinars:

Date	Webinar	Participants
15.11.2023	Webinar 1: Navigating through Network and Traffic Management: An Urban Phenomenon	42
31.01.2024	Webinar 2: Real-Time Traffic Modelling and Forecasting Tools	65
21.05.2024	Webinar 3: Transport Network Optimisation and Arbitration Models	36
30.10.2024	Webinar 4: Integrated Tool for Cooperative Traffic Management and Results of Case Study Implementation	16

Table 5: Database of TANGENT webinars moderated by Rupprecht Consult (from March 2023 to November 2024)

In regards to the AB Sessions, digital and hybrid meetings were organised with following timelines and topics (Table 6).

Date	Advisory Board Session	Format	AB Members / Participants
10.02.2023	First Advisory Board Meeting	Digital	10 / 25
22.06.2023	AB Session 1: Advancing Mode Choice Predictions: Exploring State-of-the-Art Methods and Emerging Data Sources	Digital	4 / 13
23.06.2023	AB Session 2: Advancing Mobility Strategies: State-of-the-Art Traffic Forecasting and Generation of Transport Policy and Response Plans Using Automatic Design Concept	Digital	6 / 17
26.06.2023	AB Session 3: Unlocking Data Collaboration and Assessing Smart Infrastructure Indexes	Digital	5 / 15
01.12.2023	AB Session 4: Framework for real-time traffic monitoring and forecasting: Supply Forecasting and Anomaly Detection Outputs	Digital	5 / 17
01.12.2023	AB Session 5: Initial results obtained testing individual components + Modelling of Stakeholder opinions and the formation of consensus	Digital	5 / 17
01.12.2023	AB Session 6: Update on Case Studies including current challenges in implementation + First preliminary results	Digital	5 / 17
16.10.2024	Final Event	Hybrid	AB Members: 3 Overall participants: 33 In-person / 17 online

Table 6: TANGENT Advisory Board meetings database (March 2023 - November 2024)

For further details on Forum activities, please refer to D1.5 Report on Tangent Forum Activities.

8 Post-project dissemination activities

8.1 Events, conferences and publications

The consortium will continue to promote the key results of TANGENT in the upcoming years at major conferences, events and papers to ensure a robust post-project legacy.

As the project is coming to an end, the consortium is also working on two **publications** on its key results.

- A final designed booklet summarising the main project results, outputs, and tools in an easy-to-read and concise format. This will be presented as a user-friendly brochure.
- A policy document targeted at public authorities that describes the link between multi-modal network management and policy and makes recommendations on how multimodal network management can be integrated into policy and planning processes. This will be presented as a more comprehensive and detailed brochure (approx. 28/32 pages, A4 format).

Moreover, Deusto plans to deliver a brochure focussed on showcasing the developments done in transport network optimization (WP5), showcasing the results in the different case studies. This is planned for November 2024.

8.2 Other planned activities

With the finalisation of the project the activity on the promotion and usage of the outcomes and products will be continue. Keeping TANGENT website live the consortium will make the project results open and reusable. The results and apps will be integrated and referred further in the research and development regarding the methodologies and tested technologies for traffic management; addressed to technical challenges in multimodal network and traffic management; and explore the possibility of integrated findings in the pilot cities: Rennes, Greater Manchester and Lisbon as well as the policies and governance structures behind multi-actor cooperation in traffic management.

We are planning to present the final TANGENT results and outcomes at follow scientific journals and conferences:

- Deusto plans to submit a paper to “**Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies**”. The paper will focus on **the optimization of synchronization of public transport lines along with traffic control** where we will optimize the frequency of some specified PT lines along with traffic signal timings for corresponding intersection to facilitate better traffic condition. This is helpful in situations like service disruption in one of the transport modes or special increased traffic demand scenarios like a football match or concert. We will measure the traffic state KPIs like overall delay time and PT line specific delay times, system wide emissions level and average travel time over the system to access the effectiveness of this method. It will be focussed on the testing results of Greater Manchester city simulating the morning peak hours of a football match event day.
- Imec has submitted a paper “TANGENT back-end service for real-time” to conference **11th International Conference on Vehicle** that will take place on April 2025.
- Deusto has submitted a paper “Optimization of Dynamic Congestion Pricing Strategy – A Case Study of Greater Manchester City” to American Society of Civil Engineering (ASCE) for the **International Conference on Transportation and Development** (June 2025).

9 Conclusions

The TANGENT’s communication, dissemination and exploitation activities have successfully reached the KPIs assigned in the GA and the objectives of the “D8.1 Dissemination and communication plan” developed in month three.

Throughout the duration of the project, significant emphasis was placed on establishing a strong, recognizable identity of TANGENT and ensuring its comprehensive visibility. This was accomplished by creating the informative video, regularly updating the project’s website and social media channels (X and [LinkedIn](#)), participating in European and international conferences and events, and publishing articles in academic and industry journals. Over the past 20 months, TANGENT has also cultivated close collaboration with its sister projects, the 4FRONT and MTM Clusters, through regular calls on the strategic alignment and joint participation in event sessions.

In addition, the project consortium has involved its Advisory Board and Forum in communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, including Final event, which took place 16 October 2024 at Brussels. The TANGENT visibility and exploitation activities amplify the project’s recognition and credibility in the academia. Therefore, ensuring that the project’s outcomes are noticed, valued, and adopted by industry professionals, thereby increasing its overall success and sustainability.

Communication tools	KPIs	Level of performance DoA	Level of performance M1-M38	Comment
Project website	No. of visits/ No. of followers	[800-1000/ year]/ [300/ year]	2200-2600/year	The indicator was achieved
Press releases in mass media	No. publications in the media	> 8/ project	4 + 1 scheduled in November (second period) 3 (first period)	The indicator was achieved
Social media channels	Followers/ tweets and posts	+450 followers/ 150 posts	X (former Twitter): 134 followers. LinkedIn: 511 followers. TOTAL of followers: 645 Posts: +150	The indicator was achieved
Promotional material	No. videos/ No. material designes	[1/ year]/ [3/ project]	5	A project leaflet (M3), roll-up banner (M3), banner (M3), survey leaflet, a TANGENT video (M30), an MTMC video (M32), and the final brochure . The indicator was achieved.

Communication tools	KPIs	Level of performance DoA	Level of performance M1-M38	Comment
Events	No. of presentations	[4-6/ year]/ [15/project]	>20 presentations	The indicator was achieved.
Workshops/ events/ webinars	No. of participants	>20 attendees/ workshop > 100/ project (including final event)	Total # participants (WS 1, WS 2, WS 3) Rennes: 24 (10, 7, 7) Lisbon: 26 (11, 9, 6) Manchester: 31 (21, 5, 5) Total # participants of final event: 50 Total # participants of webinars # participants 159 - W1: 42; W2: 65; W3: 36; W4: 16 290 / project (including final event)	Through virtual and on-site approach of webinars and workshops, the activities saw 150+ participants in the series of 4 webinars. For workshops, including final event policy workshop, 100+ on-site participants were present. The indicator was achieved.

Table 7: TANGENT's Key Performance Indicators on dissemination activities

10 References

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